

RomaRise: Roma Resilience: Investing in Skills and Exchange

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The first element of the **RomaRise** project brings you two beginner level courses designed to give young Roma individuals across Europe the tools, knowledge, and confidence to become active leaders and changemakers in their communities. There are still two elements to come after.

1. **General Knowledge on the EU:** This course explains how **European decisions** are made and teaches you your fundamental rights, giving you the solid foundation needed to advocate for yourself and the Roma community at a European level.

This course contains engaging videos, straightforward presentations, and quick self-assessment quizzes. It covers core topics like the European Institutional System, Governance, and Policies, alongside EU Human and Fundamental Rights, Values, and Democracy. Available in both **English** and **Greek**.

2. **Inspirational Youth Leader Talks:** These talks are meant to inspire, give fresh ideas for local activism, and show how to structure impactful messages that capture an audience's attention.

This course contains a collection of short, powerful speeches delivered to live audiences by young leaders and influencers from the **European Solidarity Corps**. These dynamic talks are recorded and available in multiple languages, covering a wide variety of social and community topics.

Check out the latest news about the project at

www.romarise.eu

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